

A Thermodynamic Study of Molecular Association by Gas-Liquid Chromatography

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Of two gas-liquid chromatographic methods, the one developed by Martire and Riedl has been used to study thermodynamic parameters of associated systems and the results with four donors and seven acceptors are presented. The donors are cetyldimethylamine (CDA), tri-n-octylamine (TOA), dialcyl ether (DLE) and dialcyl thioether (DLTE), and acceptors are ethanol, two propanols and four butanols. It has been found that glc method is as competent as any other standard method for measuring interaction of molecular association and the data obtained are systematic. The magnitude of the equilibrium constants for any particular system determined by glc method is somewhat larger and with different methods (such as calorimetry), magnitudes are different but the enthalpies of formation of molecular association are obtained close to each other indicating that the latter is less affected by side-effects. It has been concluded, therefore, that the enthalpies measured are more reliable and have been subjected to Drago's double-scale equations to compute the average electrostatic and covalent contributions.

In the recent past systematic and extensive work has been carried out as a result of which gas-liquid chromatography (glc) has gained ground as an effective and advantageous method for studying the thermodynamics of non-electrolyte solutions. It is used to make accurate and rapid measurement of association constants of organic complexes in non-aqueous solution. Two methods particularly should be mentioned in this connection and they are the one proposed by Cadogan and Purnell^{1,2} and the other independently by Martire and Riedl³. The first method appears to be more general but somewhat laborious while the second, restricted only for studying certain well-defined system, is simpler and less time-consuming. A comparative study of the two glc methods were carried out by Martire and others⁴ and it was shown that the association constants obtained through two different approaches were found in excellent agreement. This point was put forward to justify the validity of the additional assumptions made in connection with the development of the comparatively restricted Riedl-Martire method.

In Cadogan-Purnell^{1,2} method several columns containing different concentrations of nonvolatile donors D in an inert solvent I, often a high molecular weight alkane, is employed. When a volatile acceptor A reacts with the liquid phase then assuming the formation of 1 : 1 complex only one can write,

where, K_R^0 is the partition coefficient of uncomplexed A between solvent phase (S) and gas phase (G), and K_1 the

1 : 1 thermodynamic formation constant of AD in solution. Under the condition of glc experiment $a_1 \rightarrow c_1$ as $c_1 \rightarrow 0$,

$$K_1 = \frac{C_{AD}}{C_A a_D} \quad (3)$$

where, C refers to concentration and $a = \nu c$ refers to activity, ν being the activity coefficient. It can be shown that the apparent gas chromatographic partition coefficients $(K_R)_s$, assuming ideal solution behaviour of D in I ($a_D = c_D$), is given by

$$(K_R)_s = K_R^0 (1 + K_1 C_D) \quad (4)$$

$(K_R)_s$ is evaluated through the familiar glc equation,

$$V_N = (K_R)_s V_s \quad (5)$$

where, V_N is the net peak maximum retention volume and V_s the total volume of the solvent phase (D + I) in the column. Thus, from a plot of $(K_R)_s$ against C_D both K_R^0 (from intercept) and K_1 (from slope) may be obtained. If one considers the non-ideal solution behaviour, equation (4) becomes

$$(K_R)_s = (K_R^0) (1 + K_1 a_D) = K_R^0 (1 + K_1 \nu_D C_D) \quad (6)$$

where, K_R^0 and ν_D would now be function of C_D . Taking K_R^0 and ν_D to be polynomials in C_D and keeping terms through first power of C_D only, equation (6) becomes

$$(K_R)_s = (K_R)_I [1 + (\alpha_1 + K_1) C_D] \quad (7)$$

where, $K_R^0 = (K_R)_I (1 + \alpha_1 C_D + \dots)$, $(K_R)_I$ being the partition coefficient of A between pure I and gas phase, and $\nu_D = 1 + \beta_1 C_D + \dots$. From equation (7) one now obtains $K_1 + \alpha_1$ instead of K_1 .

Eon *et al.*^{5,6} suggested an expression,

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$$\alpha_1 = v_A \left[1 - \frac{v_D}{v_1} \right] \quad (8)$$

where, v_i 's are the molar volumes of the respective components. Their analysis suggests that either (a) the donor and inert solvent be chosen to have the same molar volume, where $\alpha_1 = 0$, or (b) equation (8) be used to approximate α_1 .

In Martire-Riedl method³ only two pure columns, one with non-volatile electron donor D and another a reference alkane column, are employed. The reference alkane is chosen in such a way that $v_D \approx v_1$. The equilibrium constant K_1 , of 1 : 1 association reaction,

can be written as

$$K_1 = \frac{C_{AD}}{C_A a_D}$$

as before for glc experiments. Since the solvent activity remains unchanged by the complex formation,

$$K_1 a_D = K' = \frac{C_{AD}}{C_A} \quad (9)$$

If x is the fraction of solute complexed,

$$x = \frac{C_{AD}}{C_A + C_{AD}}$$

we get,

$$\frac{1}{1-x} = K' + 1 \quad (10)$$

The specific retention volume of a solute which forms a 1 : 1 complex with the liquid phase is now⁷

$$V_g^o = \frac{273R}{v_2^a p_2^o M_1} = \frac{273R}{v_2 (1-x) p_2^o M_1} = \frac{273R}{v_2 p_2^o M_1} (K' + 1) \quad (11)$$

where, v_2' is the apparent (experimentally measured) solute activity coefficient and v_2 the actual activity coefficient of uncomplexed solute molecules. If one now defines four different specific retention volumes,

$$V_g^{oa} = \frac{273R}{v_2^a p_2^o M^a}$$

(acceptor solute in reference non-polar solvent)

$$V_g^{ob} = \frac{273R}{v_2^b p_2^o M^b} (K' + 1)$$

(acceptor solute in donor solvent)

$$\bar{V}_g^{oa} = \frac{273R}{v_2^a p_2^o M^a}$$

(non-polar solute in reference non-polar solvent)

$$\bar{V}_g^{ob} = \frac{273R}{v_2^b p_2^o M^b}$$

(non-polar solute in donor solvent)
one may have the relation,

$$\frac{V_g^{ob} \times \bar{V}_g^{oa}}{V_g^{oa} \times \bar{V}_g^{ob}} = \frac{v_2^b v_2^a}{v_2^a v_2^b} (1 + K') \quad (12)$$

It has been shown³ that for any non-polar solute in two different solvents of the same size, shape, molar volume and polarizability, the activity coefficient ratio depends primarily on the pairwise potential energies between the solvent molecules and is essentially independent of the solute. This suggests

$$\frac{v_2^a}{v_2^b} = \frac{\bar{v}_2^a}{\bar{v}_2^b} \quad (13)$$

Combined with equation (12) this gives

$$\frac{V_g^{ob} \bar{V}_g^{oa}}{V_g^{oa} \bar{V}_g^{ob}} = K' + 1 \quad (14)$$

In order to calculate K_1 from equation (14), one has to know a_D , the activity of the pure electron donor, where $a_D = C_D v_D$. v_D based on the concentration convention is given by³

$$v_D = \frac{\bar{V}_g^{ob}}{\bar{V}_g^{oa}} \cdot \frac{M^b}{M^a} \quad (15)$$

C_D 's can be calculated knowing the densities of the pure electron donor at different temperatures. Finally, the equilibrium constant is determined from the relation,

$$K_1 = \frac{K'}{a_D} = \frac{K'}{C_D v_D} \quad (16)$$

However, later Martire pointed out⁸ that equation (13) is not quite justifiable and equation (12) should be used as such with equation (16) still valid. The value of the activity coefficient ratio turns out to be $1 + \alpha_1 C_D + (\alpha_1^2/2) C_D^2$ with $v_D \approx v_1$. Also v_D is close to unity and can be taken as $v_D \approx 1 + \beta_1 C_D$. Equation (12) now becomes

$$\frac{V_g^{ob} \bar{V}_g^{oa}}{V_g^{oa} \bar{V}_g^{ob}} = 1 + (K_1 + \alpha_1) C_D + [K_1(\alpha_1 + \beta_1) + \alpha_1^2/2] C_D^2 \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) has the advantage of requiring only relative measurements on two columns but has potential disadvantage that C_D^2 term with pure D may not be negligible. With C_D^2 term assumed negligible, both Martire and Purnell ap-

proaches give the sum $(K_1 + \alpha_1) = K$ as the apparent association constant*.

In this communication the results of the study on molecular association of four electron donors with seven aliphatic alcohols have been presented. The studies have been carried out by the Martire-Riedl glc method keeping in mind that the study would act as a probe in the efficacy and reliability of the method. Of the two glc methods, the Martire-Riedl method has been chosen which is more specific of the two in application and is less general but is more simple and less time-consuming. A few of the systems reported have also been studied calorimetrically in order to enable a comparison and reported in a separate communication¹⁵. The system chosen for study are also characterised by the facts that (i) two tertiary amines have been chosen as electron donors to interact with the same alcohols, varying the size of the molecule with an increase in the number of carbon atoms and (ii) one amine, one ether and one thioether with same number of carbon atoms have been studied against the same alcohols as proton donors.

Results and Discussion

The polarizabilities were calculated from electronic bond polarizabilities given by Le Fevre and Steel⁹. The method of calculation is discussed by Smith¹⁰. The molar volumes at 60° and polarizabilities are given in Table 1. The molar volumes were calculated from the densities determined by pycnometry. The densities are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—MOLAR VOLUMES AND POLARIZABILITIES OF SOLVENTS

Solvent	Molar volume (V_g^0) ml molecule ⁻¹ at 60°	Polarizability (α_0) ml molecule ⁻¹ $\times 10^{25}$
Nonadecane	351.6	349.8
Cetyldimethylamine	345.7	346.1
Tetracosane	435.0	435.8
Tri-n-octylamine	448.5	454.0
Dilauryl ether	441.9	446.6
Dilauryl thioether	449.5	469.8

Infinite dilution V_g^0 values for seven alcohol and three non-polar alkane solutes mentioned above were determined for each liquid phase polar and non-polar columns at various temperatures. For nonadecane, cetyldimethylamine (CDA) and tri-n-octylamine (TOA) data were obtained at

*The gas chromatographic method provides an apparent equilibrium constant which comprises (i) the H-bonded complex formation constant represented by K_1 (vide equation 2) and (ii) the contact pair formation constant represented by α_1 . While K_1 is the chemical equilibrium constant, α_1 represents the short-lived contact pair formed by van der Waals forces. Therefore ΔH and ΔG terms determined from the temperature variation of $K_1 + \alpha_1$ should be treated as apparent. Hence we refrained from using ΔH^0 and ΔG^0 notations. In fact, $\Delta H = (K_1 \Delta H^0 + \alpha_1 \Delta H_{\alpha_1}) / (K_1 + \alpha_1)$.

TABLE 2—DENSITY OF THE LIQUID PHASE ($g\ ml^{-1}$) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Compd.	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°
Nonadecane	0.782	0.776	0.769	0.763	0.756
Cetyldimethylamine	0.799	0.792	0.786	0.779	0.772
Tetracosane	0.798	0.791	0.784	0.778	0.771
Tri-n-octylamine	0.808	0.801	0.795	0.788	0.782
Dilauryl ether	0.822	0.816	0.809	0.802	0.795
Dilauryl thioether	0.844	0.838	0.831	0.824	0.817

30, 40, 50, 60 and 70°, whereas for dilauryl ether (DLE) it was 40, 50, 60 and 70°, for dilauryl thioether (DLTE) it was 45, 50, 60 and 70° and for tetracosane columns experiments were carried out at 55, 60, 65 and 70°. The specific retention volumes at lower temperatures (i.e. 30, 40° etc.) were then calculated from least square linear regression of $\log V_g^0$ against $1/T$. However, it is to be noted that when the extrapolation has to be made over a wide temperature range this method is not acceptable. The values of least square method V_g^0 at different temperatures are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—INFINITE DILUTION BULK SPECIFIC RETENTION VOLUMES (V_g^0 , ml g⁻¹) IN NONADECANE, TETRACOSANE, CETYLDIMETHYLAMINE, TRI-N-OCTYLAMINE, DILAURYL ETHER AND DILAURYL THIOETHER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solute component	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°
<i>In nonadecane :</i>					
Ethanol	23.35	18.05	13.90	10.82	8.78
n-Propanol	79.25	58.15	43.44	32.23	25.95
Isopropanol	44.57	33.51	25.45	19.52	15.18
n-Butanol	262.2	182.5	130.0	93.08	67.95
Isobutanol	181.0	127.3	92.34	68.45	50.80
sec-Butanol	160.9	114.2	83.22	60.68	44.96
t-Butanol	75.86	55.80	40.93	31.45	24.44
3-Methylpentane	316.1	216.5	150.9	110.9	79.84
2,3-Dimethylbutane	255.9	181.6	129.9	93.22	70.24
2,2-Dimethylbutane	181.5	129.2	94.15	70.34	52.22
<i>In tetracosane :</i>					
Ethanol	20.83	15.88	12.32	9.70	7.74
n-Propanol	72.61	53.25	39.81	30.28	23.41
Isopropanol	41.57	31.02	23.57	18.21	14.28
n-Butanol	231.8	159.5	112.3	80.72	59.18
Isobutanol	160.1	112.5	80.73	59.11	44.09
sec-Butanol	146.4	100.9	71.10	51.17	37.55
t-Butanol	70.02	50.77	37.46	28.15	21.51
3-Methylpentane	250.1	177.2	128.2	94.56	70.99
2,3-Dimethylbutane	216.6	154.0	111.8	82.69	62.26
2,2-Dimethylbutane	146.0	107.1	80.09	60.94	47.11
<i>In cetyldimethylamine</i>					
Ethanol	320.6	188.9	114.5	71.32	45.97
n-Propanol	1070	601.4	343.6	204.9	126.2
Isopropanol	410.9	240.5	149.3	92.1	60.55
n-Butanol	3603	1892	1042	602.8	352.1
Isobutanol	2326	1270	738.2	432	265.4

Table-3(contd)

sec-Butanol	1344	756.4	431.6	263.7	160.1
t-Butanol	464.6	273.9	170.8	111.2	72.20
3-Methylpentane	311.1	212.0	145.8	108.1	76.48
2,3-Dimethylbutane	250.8	176.3	126.2	89.98	66.70
2,2-Dimethylbutane	180.2	127.7	92.03	67.31	50.45
<i>In tri-n-octylamine :</i>					
Ethanol	483.2	283.1	171.5	104.4	67.11
n-Propanol	1466	832.0	486.9	297.2	184.4
Isopropanol	605.4	352.3	213.5	132.8	84.92
n-Butanol	4788	2566	1424	820.4	486.3
Isobutanol	2748	1542	893.2	533.4	328.8
sec-Butanol	1686	964.9	555.7	343.6	210.5
t-Butanol	672.8	388.0	236.1	148.3	93.76
3-Methylpentane	254.2	177.6	125.9	93.48	70.15
2,3-Dimethylbutane	217.2	153.2	112.2	82.20	61.16
2,2-Dimethylbutane	150.1	109.5	80.57	59.86	45.74
<i>In dilauryl ether :</i>					
Ethanol	-	59.86	39.69	27.49	19.26
n-Propanol	-	174.3	111.4	75.30	50.61
Isopropanol	-	81.69	55.42	38.22	26.80
n-Butanol	-	585.8	352.7	226.6	145.3
Isobutanol	-	393.2	245.5	156.8	104.8
sec-Butanol	-	274.4	172.5	112.2	74.94
t-Butanol	-	114.8	75.94	52.37	36.81
3-Methylpentane	-	183.6	129.5	95.18	69.90
2,3-Dimethylbutane	-	157.0	113.9	81.58	60.87
2,2-Dimethylbutane	-	108.5	80.06	60.69	46.81
<i>In dilauryl thioether :</i>					
Ethanol	-	-	28.22	20.30	14.85
n-Propanol	-	-	91.27	63.94	45.16
Isopropanol	-	-	47.26	34.21	25.57
n-Butanol	-	-	273.4	182.6	124.1
Isobutanol	-	-	175.3	121.5	82.70
sec-Butanol	-	-	137.9	91.92	63.21
t-Butanol	-	-	69.97	49.87	35.88
3-Methylpentane	-	-	121.1	91.28	67.78
2,3-Dimethylbutane	-	-	107.3	78.82	59.61
2,2-Dimethylbutane	-	-	77.23	58.24	45.64

It was found that the V_g^{0+} s were independent of f^{-1} and an average of the four V_g^{0+} s were taken for the infinite dilution bulk specific retention volume. The standard deviation was nearly 1% excepting those for ethanol which showed greater scatter. This may be due to comparatively smaller retention times in the case of ethanol. In Table 4 the values for V_g^{0+}/V_g^{0b} are provided. These are taken as the average values of the ratios of the specific retention volumes of the three alkane solutes in the reference alkane and donor solvent respectively. The association constant (K) were then determined through equations (14) to (16). The values of K for various systems at different temperatures are given in Table 5. It was estimated that the prob-

 TABLE 4-VALUES OF $\bar{V}_g^{0+}/\bar{V}_g^{0b}$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

System	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°
Cetyldimethylamine-alcohols	1.014	1.021	1.029	1.036	1.044
Tri-n-octylamine-alcohols	0.984	0.993	1.004	1.012	1.020
Dilauryl ether-alcohols	-	0.975	0.991	1.004	1.015
Dilauryl thioether-alcohols	-	-	1.046	1.044	1.041

able error in the tabulated K values for CDA + alcohol and TOA + alcohol complexes is about 3% while for DLE + alcohol and DLTE + alcohol complexes about 4%. The ΔH and ΔS for association were then found out from least square linear regression of $\log K$ against $1/T$. The least square ΔH and ΔS are set out in Table 6, along with the corresponding standard deviations. One graphical representations of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ with the least squares lines for TOA-alcohol systems are provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ with the least squares best fit line for TOA-alcohol systems: (O) ethanol, (Δ) n-propanol, (\square) isopropanol, (\bullet) n-butanol, (\blacktriangle) isobutanol, (\blacksquare) sec-butanol and (\blacktriangle) t-butanol systems.

 TABLE 5-EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS (K , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) OF DIFFERENT SYSTEMS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Alcohol	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°
<i>Cetyldimethylamine-alcohol system :</i>					
Ethanol	4.39	3.34	2.62	2.08	1.62
n-Propanol	4.32	3.30	2.50	1.99	1.48
Isopropanol	2.84	2.18	1.77	1.38	1.14
n-Butanol	4.40	3.31	2.54	2.03	1.60
Isobutanol	4.09	3.17	2.54	1.97	1.61
sec-Butanol	2.54	1.99	1.52	1.25	0.98
t-Butanol	1.77	1.38	1.15	0.95	0.75
<i>Tri-n-octylamine-alcohol system :</i>					
Ethanol	8.99	7.00	5.54	4.29	3.46

Table-5 (contd)

n-Propanol	7.77	6.08	4.82	3.88	3.10
Isopropanol	5.50	4.30	3.46	2.77	2.23
n-Butanol	7.96	6.27	5.01	4.03	3.25
Isobutanol	6.54	5.28	4.32	3.53	2.91
sec-Butanol	4.25	3.56	2.92	2.51	2.08
t-Butanol	3.47	2.76	2.27	1.88	1.52
<i>Dilauryl ether-alcohol system :</i>					
Ethanol	-	1.08	0.909	0.782	0.659
n-Propanol	-	0.886	0.735	0.634	0.516
Isopropanol	-	0.634	0.551	0.469	0.391
n-Butanol	-	1.04	0.876	0.770	0.645
Isobutanol	-	0.974	0.835	0.705	0.610
sec-Butanol	-	0.668	0.582	0.509	0.443
t-Butanol	-	0.487	0.418	0.368	0.318
<i>Dilauryl thioether-alcohol system :</i>					
Ethanol	-	-	0.595	0.508	0.430
n-Propanol	-	-	0.596	0.516	0.435
Isopropanol	-	-	0.468	0.412	0.373
n-Butanol	-	-	0.659	0.584	0.510
Isobutanol	-	-	0.542	0.491	0.411
sec-Butanol	-	-	0.432	0.375	0.324
t-Butanol	-	-	0.406	0.364	0.318

The equilibrium constants (K) given in Table 5 reveal certain trends which are as follows : (i) K decreases with increasing carbon number of the alcohol, (ii) K decreases in going from the primary to the tertiary alcohol of the same carbon number and (iii) K also decreased with the rise of temperature from 30 to 70° in a given alcohol-amine system implying the reactions are exothermic. These are readily explainable by known inductive and steric effects of the alcohol alkyl groups.

The acidity of the alcohols, as reported by Murto¹¹, expressed in the form of pK_a values shows the following trend : ethanol > n-propanol \approx n-butanol \approx isobutanol > isopropanol > sec-butanol > t-butanol. The order of K values in the four butyl alcohol is : n-butanol > isobutanol > sec-butanol > t-butanol. Murto provided the proton donating abilities of the various alcohols in terms of their pK_a 's. It is apparent that, though not very clear, a semblance of parallelism exists between the pK_a values and the equilibrium constants.

As observed by Pimentel and McClellan and Patterson *et al.*, there also exists a parallelism between ΔH and ΔS for all the systems under consideration (Table 6)¹². As reported by other workers¹² this is in conformity with the fact that a stronger bonding (and hence a larger $-\Delta H$) requires a favourable and restricted spatial arrangement of the molecules hence a greater order leading to a larger value of $-\Delta S$. The ΔH values are nearly the expected ones for such systems and comparable to the values provided by

Liao and Martire^{13,14} for N..H-O bonds obtained from similar systems where this bond is formed. In passing from CDA to TOA, there is a fall in the values of $|\Delta H|$ though small. The K values in our systems are larger than those for the systems of Martire. However, the association constants determined by the flow calorimetric technique¹⁵ for CDA-n-propanol and CDA-n-butanol systems are fairly in agreement with our glc values while that for TOA-n-propanol is larger. The ΔH values determined calorimetrically are slightly larger. For DLE systems, ΔH and ΔS values are, however, within the range of the values normally found for O..H-O bonds^{12,16}. The results of these systems are also more or less in agreement with the data for similar systems reported by Liao and Martire¹³. For DLTE system, ΔH values are also nearly the anticipated ones for such systems and are comparable to the values obtained by Liao and Martire¹³ for similar systems. There is, however, not a very clear trend in ΔS values as one passes from one alcohol to another suggesting that possibly several factors contribute to the magnitude of ΔH . Also as observed by Liao and Martire¹³, the magnitudes of ΔH suggest that the thioethers as bases are stronger than they were thought to be. Fig. 2 shows the graphical plot of $(-\Delta H)$ vs $(-\Delta S)$ with the least square best fit line which is

$$(-\Delta S) = 1.41 \times 10^{-3} (-\Delta H) + (-6.11) \quad (18)$$

with a standard deviation (σ) of 0.95.

Fig. 2. Plot of $-\Delta S$ vs $-\Delta H$ with least squares best fit line : (Δ) DLTE-alcohols, (O) DLE-alcohols, (□) TOA-alcohols and (●) CDA-alcohols systems.

TABLE 6-ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY OF FORMATION OF DIFFERENT SYSTEMS IN THE TEMPERATURE RANGE 30-70°

	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
<i>Cetyldimethylamine-alcohol system :</i>		
Ethanol	5.11 ± 0.07	13.90 ± 0.23
n-Propanol	5.46 ± 0.17	15.09 ± 0.52
Isopropanol	4.68 ± 0.08	13.39 ± 0.24
n-Butanol	5.19 ± 0.06	14.18 ± 0.18
Isobutanol	4.82 ± 0.07	13.10 ± 0.21
sec-Butanol	4.88 ± 0.09	14.23 ± 0.29
t-Butanol	4.30 ± 0.14	13.05 ± 0.43

Table-6 (contd.)

<i>Tri-n-octyl amine-alcohol system :</i>		
Ethanol	4.95 ± 0.08	11.96 ± 0.24
n-Propanol	4.72 ± 0.04	11.49 ± 0.13
Isopropanol	4.63 ± 0.05	11.90 ± 0.14
n-Butanol	4.61 ± 0.04	11.07 ± 0.12
Isobutanol	4.17 ± 0.04	10.03 ± 0.13
sec-Butanol	3.67 ± 0.09	9.22 ± 0.27
t-Butanol	4.21 ± 0.08	11.40 ± 0.26
<i>Dilauryl ether-alcohol system :</i>		
Ethanol	3.49 ± 0.08	11.00 ± 0.26
n-Propanol	3.77 ± 0.20	12.29 ± 0.61
Isopropanol	3.43 ± 0.21	11.85 ± 0.64
n-Butanol	3.36 ± 0.16	10.64 ± 0.50
Isobutanol	3.36 ± 0.07	10.77 ± 0.21
sec-Butanol	2.92 ± 0.06	10.11 ± 0.18
t-Butanol	3.00 ± 0.06	11.01 ± 0.20
<i>Dilauryl thioether-alcohol system :</i>		
Ethanol	3.45 ± 0.11	11.71 ± 0.34
n-Propanol	3.37 ± 0.15	11.47 ± 0.44
Isopropanol	2.65 ± 0.12	9.69 ± 0.39
n-Butanol	2.87 ± 0.08	9.70 ± 0.24
Isobutanol	3.13 ± 0.30	10.88 ± 0.92
sec-Butanol	3.11 ± 0.06	11.30 ± 0.17
t-Butanol	2.58 ± 0.15	9.78 ± 0.46

Comparative studies of the glc method with the spectroscopic ones have shown that though the glc association constants are quite consistent and offer a better basis for interpretation of the data in terms of acid base behaviour³, yet the values of glc K appears to be larger than the corresponding spectroscopic values^{8,17} and may be given by $K_1 + \alpha_1$. If the complexes are strong, i.e. $K_1 \gg \alpha_1$, the glc (or thermodynamic) association constant becomes nearly equal to the values derived spectroscopically, whereas if the complexes are weak α_1 can not be neglected. Moreover, it is well known that the concentration of weak complexes in solution cannot be determined from thermodynamic measurements alone¹⁸ without the aid of a detailed model and glc method is no exception to this. To account for the apparent discrepancies, Martire⁸ proposed that glc values are a measure of the total effect of donor-acceptor interactions, chemical plus physical, whereas spectroscopy gives only chemical interactions¹⁹⁻²¹. Purnell, on the other hand, proposed in his microscopic partition (MP) theory^{22,23} that liquids A (acceptor) and S (solvent) exist in their macroscopic solution as microscopically immiscible groups of like molecules. The partition coefficient is composed of a volume fraction weighted partition coefficients of solute D (donor) between pure liquid A and S respectively. It was possible to correlate the glc, nmr, uv-visible approaches for

determination of formation constants by the MP theory²⁴. In spite of those attempts much remains unknown regarding the exact nature of equilibrium constant, derived from various sources.

From the foregoing discussions and also from the closeness of the ΔH values rather than the experimental K 's for some systems, determined both by glc (this work) method and calorimetry¹⁵, it appears that side-effects are least in the determination of ΔH . Some authors²⁵ have chosen to represent the stability of the complex in terms of the strengths of the acid and base with expression,

$$\log K = S_A S_D + \sigma_A \sigma_D \quad (19)$$

where, S_A and S_D are the strengths of the acid and base; σ_A and σ_D are parameters characterising the 'hardness' and 'softness' of the acid and base. But we prefer to accept the contention of Drago *et al.*^{26,27} wherein they have taken the thermal effect of the reaction ($-\Delta H$) as a stability measure of the complex instead of the equilibrium constant,

$$-\Delta H = E_A E_D + C_A C_D \quad (20)$$

where parameters E_A and E_D are related to the electrostatic properties and parameter C_A and C_D are to the covalent properties, of the acceptor and donor molecules which form 1 : 1 complex. Products $E_A E_D$ and $C_A C_D$ characterise the contributions of the electrostatic and covalent interactions respectively to the AD bond. This is also in agreement with Mulliken's observation²⁸ that the wave functions of a complex, to a first approximation, is represented in the form of two components, the one corresponding to an electrostatic interaction, and the other corresponding to a covalent bond. Drago and Wayland²⁶ took the iodine molecule as the standard acceptor and assumed $E_A = C_A = 1$. The enthalpies of iodine with a series of alkylamines were then used to determine the donor properties of the amines. It was assumed that $E_D = a\mu_D$ and $C_D = bR_D$, where μ_D is the dipole moment and R_D the refraction of the amine related to the dipole moment and the polarizability of the lone electron pair respectively. Thus a system of equations of two unknowns, a and b were obtained for a series of complexes of iodine with amines. The solution for energy pair of equations yielded a and b and the average value was taken for each of them. From these values of a and b , E_D and C_D of those amines were obtained. From the heats of formation of these amines with other acceptors the E_A and C_A for the said acceptors can be calculated. These in turn can be used to obtain E_D and C_D for other donors once the enthalpies of their complex formation with the said acceptors are known. It is to be noted here that $-\Delta H$ used in the double scale equation mentioned above should be the true value and free of all side-effects. Drago *et al.*^{26,27} showed that the double scale enthalpy equation has a definite advan-

tage over the 'Hard and Soft Acid-Base Model' for it not only predicts the relative hardness or softness of an acid or base through the *C/E* ratios but also predicts the strength of any acid-base pair whose parameters are known. If *C/E* is fairly high, the acid or base is classified as soft and for the reverse case they are classified as hard.

TABLE 7—ACID AND BASE PARAMETERS FOR DRAGO'S DOUBLE SCALE ENTHALPY EQUATION

Acid	Parameter		Base	Parameter	
	E_A	C_A		E_D	C_D
n-Propanol	2.77	0.24	CDA	1.0	10.89
Isopropanol	3.14	0.15	TOA	1.0	8.55
n-Butanol	2.78	0.21	DLE	1.1	1.95
Isobutanol	2.39	0.22	DLTE	0.3	10.48
sec-Butanol	1.67	0.27			
t-Butanol	2.70	0.16			

The experimentally determined enthalpies in this work for 24 systems, between four electron donors and six alcohols have been subjected to Drago's double scale equation. As the E_D 's are parameters of dipole moment and alkyl substituents have negligible effect on E_D , we have taken Drago's²⁹ E_D values for triethylamine, di-n-butyl ether and diethyl thioether as E_D 's for our amines, ether and thioether respectively. With trial values for C_D , solutions were obtained for E_A and C_A . The retrieved values were then again used for a fresh solution for C_D which in turn was used to recalculate E_A and C_A . The process was continued till the average difference for the experimentally determined and calculated enthalpies converged to a minimum. Table 7 shows the E_A, C_A and E_D, C_D values for the acids and bases respectively. The average deviation between the calculated and experimental enthalpies is 0.17 kcal mol⁻¹. Table 8 gives the averaged of electrostatic ($E_A E_D$) and covalent ($C_A C_D$) contributions to the enthalpy. The averages are those for all the alcohols interacting with each donor. It is found that for DLE-alcohol systems electrostatic contributions are largest and it decreases in the order of TOA and CDA and finally with DLTE-alcohol systems the covalent contribution predominates. Also as calculated by *C/E* ratio, the order of hardness of different bases is: DLE > TOA > CDA > DLTE. These facts are in agreement with the observation that hard acids and bases react predominantly electrostatically and soft acids and bases react predominantly covalently.

TABLE 8—AVERAGE ELECTROSTATIC AND COVALENT CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE ENTHALPY (IN%) FOR DONOR-ALCOHOL COMPLEXES

System	Electrostatic	Covalent
	($E_A E_D$)	($C_A C_D$)
CDA-Alcohols	53.7	46.3
TOA-Alcohols	59.1	40.9
DLE-Alcohols	87.5	12.5
DLTE-Alcohols	26.1	73.9

In conclusion, the glc *K* values though found large are systematically so and are consistent among themselves. Thus the *K*'s are meaningful for interpretation and the ΔH values determined from them are the anticipated ones and as good as those determined by any other method. Both the Martire-Riedl method and the Cadogan-Purnell method are equally suitable for studying association phenomenon but the latter appears to be more general of the two. The disadvantage of using a specified alkane reference solvent with the Martire-Riedl method restricts the method itself. The glc methods on the whole, are as competent as any other method for studying association phenomenon like hydrogen bonding keeping in mind that the methods can be used when one of the components is non-volatile and the other volatile. The results obtained by these methods are as meaningful as those obtained by other standard methods and can be subjected to analysis and interpretation.

Experimental

The dual column glc apparatus used in the experiments was designed and fabricated in this laboratory²⁹. The columns and thermal conductivity detector were housed in an oil and an air thermostat respectively. The temperature of the column-bath was controlled within $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The thermal conductivity detector was kept at 200°. The column inlet and outlet pressures were measured by two mercury manometers. A precision flow regulator was used to control the flow of the carrier gas and its rate was measured by a soap-film flowmeter. The injection port temperature was kept at 225°. Hydrogen was the carrier gas.

Preparation of the column: The solid support material was chromosorb-W, 60–80 mesh, acid washed and DMCS treated. The support was coated with liquid phases in the usual manner³⁰ and packed into copper tubings (0.25" o.d.). These were about 5 ft long with alkanes columns while with amines columns lengths were about 2.5 ft. The exact liquid load for each column was determined by ashing³ or by Soxhlet extraction method.

Specific retention volume measurement: Specific retention volume, V_g^0 (ml g⁻¹) was calculated using the method of Littlewood *et al.*³⁰,

$$V_g^0 = \frac{f}{W_L} \cdot \frac{273.16}{T_r} \cdot \frac{P_o - P_w}{P_o} \cdot \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{(P_1/P_o)^2 - 1}{(P_1/P_o)^3 - 1} \right] \quad (21)$$

where, *f* is the flow rate of the carrier gas (ml s⁻¹), W_L the weight of liquid phase (g), P_o the column outlet pressure, P_1 the column inlet pressure, P_w the vapour pressure of water at room temperature T_r (K). V_g^0 thus obtained was corrected for adsorption of the solute on the solid support-liquid phase interface and the gas-liquid interface that may exist. For the first, for a given column, several elution peaks corresponding to sample size 0.5 to 5.0 μ l were recorded.

The infinite dilution peak maximum retention time was obtained by extrapolation to zero sample size²⁹. In this way V_g^0 corrected for support adsorption, were determined in four different columns with varying amounts of liquid phase for the same liquid. These were then plotted against the reciprocal weight fraction, f^{-1} of the liquid phase^{13,14}. The desired infinite dilution bulk specific retention volume corrected for adsorption on solid-liquid and liquid-gas interfaces were obtained from the intercept, i.e. for infinite loading.

Cetyldimethylamine (CDA), tri-n-octylamine (TOA), dilauryl ether (DLE), dilauryl thioether (DLTE), nonadecane ($n-C_{19}H_{40}$) and tetracosane ($n-C_{24}H_{50}$) were used as liquid phase. Nonadecane and tetracosane were chosen as the reference alkane solvent, nonadecane for CDA and tetracosane for TOA, DLE and DLTE respectively. CDA (obtained from Societe de Usines Chimiques, Paris), TOA, DLTE, nonadecane and tetracosane (all Aldrich) were further purified by vacuum distillation and stored in dark-colored bottles in a refrigerator. DLE used was synthesised by the Organic Chemistry Department of this Institute.

Ten solutes were used : ethanol, n-propanol, isopropanol, n-butanol, isobutanol, sec-butanol, t-butanol, 3-methylpentane, 2,2-dimethylbutane and 2,3-dimethylbutane. The alcohols were all analytical grade reagents and used as such. The three alkane solutes (Aldrich, 99% purity) were also used as such.

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